

Switch to EPEMCtm 2

Stages and Evolution of the EPEMC Paradigm switch, in brief

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ABSTRACT

The previous work on the Extended Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology has yielded good work in establishing the why to switch. Within the first iteration of the cosmology, all of the major “Electric Universe” materials were covered, and the dark universe debunking, etc. was able to occur. Also there was an engineering of paper standards and they evolved as well.

Within the second iteration of the cosmology there arose more proofs and addendums, and there was at the end, a flowering and birth of the other series. Now as the cosmology enters its third iteration, the author/architect of the cosmology would like to lay out the past roadmap, and the future roadmap for the cosmology, so that this work can be carried on by many, and effectively.

Key words: Electric Universe - EPEMC - MIMS - SPACER - Paradigm - Cosmology - Evolution

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First Iteration

Standards set

The first thing set forward as the first papers were written were a set of standards:

- Cite all ideas possible
- Use engineering and internet ready standard: footnotes with direct links
- Where possible, cite page numbers if necessary
- Attribute credit for images and figures and numbers
- For the author's papers, list all of them at beginning of references and use [#] system
 - Deprecated
- Be available to rebuttal, and provide all spreadsheets for open data
- Stick to strict scientific method

Topics covered

In the beginning, the EPEMC entered into primarily "Electric Universe" dealings, but with a more engineered pathway than the latter in order to avoid the polarization issues:

- ❖ On the Origins of Religions (genesis of EPEMC) series
 - Unboxing Atlantis
 - Dealing with aliens etc.
- ❖ Plasmaglyphics and Megafauna Extinction series
 - Hopewell Octagons proof the Earth flipped over
- ❖ Magnetic Universe Theory (series includes PEMS & HEGEME theory)
- ❖ Dark Universe Debunking
- ❖ Chinese Plasmascriptic series
- ❖ EPEMC series
- ❖ Charge Distributive Networks and bioenergetic series (TESLAB)
- ❖ King Arthur series
- ❖ SPACER series started
- ❖ Miscellaneous

- ❖ EU Gateway 1.0 (deprecated)
- ❖ Maps:
 - King Arthur Conspiracy
 - Eastern Tribes of Native America
 - Giants of EU History

Second Iteration

In the second iteration of the EPEMC, aside from the dropping of the citation of the author standard, the author spent a lot of time refining the look of the series. In particular the addition of animations become standard if possible, along with the provision of bitly links for the papers on page 1, to the google docs, etc.

- ❖ Addition of gifs
- ❖ Creation of more slides
- ❖ Release of pre-EPEMC materials to “draft” section of the Academia page of the author

Topics covered

The second iteration tended to add addendums for the most part:

- Retraction of moon as origin for thunderbolts event,
- Promotion of the Shamash hypothesis
 - ◆ Presentations, papers, and data given publicly
- Increased coverage of EPEMC in shows
- Refinement of the various series
- Odd sites, OOPArts, etc.
- Strategy Series
- Electrogeology Series (combined with AKHA¹ work)
- EPEMC tools like tables and figures collected
- MIMS 1.0
 - ◆ Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual (philosophy)
- SPACER Standard
 - ◆ Fruit of the AIM™ thinktank standards
- Plasma-electromagnetic Gateway 2.0
 - ◆ Social media
 - ◆ Educational series
 - ◆ Catalog and numerous features
 - ◆ Deprecated (author fired web designer)
- Maps: (publicly released)
 - ◆ Top 50 Megaliths
 - ◆ Ancient Sites of the World

Third (current) Iteration

In the third iteration the flowering of several ideas and the fruit of the MIMS philosophy, as well as new directions and focuses. There was also a new series of EPEMC tools created.

- ❖ EPEMC Paper Directory

¹ Ancient Kentucke Historical Association (~1992, J. Michaels), inheritor of the work of famous altstream foundation: Filson Historical Society (Louisville, KY)

- Tools and resources added
- ❖ More incisive critique of altstream and mainstream
- ❖ Shift in focus of DUD towards the Peer Review and General Relativity cults
- ❖ Increased Mimsical Analysis
- ❖ The Pulse Show (podcast)

Topics covered

- MIMS 2.0+
 - Especial data driven analyses or related to Operations Research
- Strategy Series
 - New Cold War Series
- SPACER Series
 - Conquering the Solar System
- Business Series
 - Publication of the Starter Grower tool
- PEMS 2
 - Ashes of Atlantis Series
- Continued PEMS and HEGEME
- Miscellaneous religious and other topics (aliens, etc.)
- Strategy Series book “To Loot a Burning House” published
- Explication of Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis
- EPEMC Gateway 3.0 (current)
- PEM World Expo
- Plans to be laid for other analyses
- Maps:
 - Electrogeology
 - US Military Empire

EPEMC Evolution

None of the EPEMC documents deprecate in the true sense of the word. They only evolve. So, for example in iteration 1, we had the Electric Universe Primer and the EU Gateway. In iteration 2 we had the new Gateway (electricpulse.com) and the Electric Universe Memo. In the third iteration there was the introduction of the FAQ, directory and Gateway 3.0 (epemcgateway.com) and the EPEMC vs. EU paradigm comparison paper. Essentially EPEMC has been design to do what Electric Universe cannot: evolve and adapt, synthesize and depolarize. To do so, there is an increased fair and open critique of alternative altstream options, and in short, there are none and Electric Universe itself comes up short. One day EPEMC may be deprecated for a “The Force” cosmology, however, MIMS as a philosophy has already covered why this would be a mistake: the Force is only one of the six powers of the “Big G” data diagram, which was proven internally consistent as well as philosophically self-consistent with the MIMS philosophy, which itself is mimsically self-consistent.

The author’s personal evolution will be to move into the world of operations research, data, and of course the strategy series and more MIMS. A MIMS book will be forthcoming. There will be some more time spent in critiquing the altstream and mainstream, as well as more explication of electrogeology and looking deeper into Atlantis. Also the Hidden Kentucky book should become published this year or next.

Conclusion

There is ever more a compelling reason to leave the Standard Model and abandon the mainstream for the altstream. Without talking specific events from 2019-2022, it is clear to most people that the lies of the mainstream make their paradigms untenable for human survival, and the EPEMC open-source-cosmology standard is more social media friendly, and free speech oriented. Therefore, the author forecasts continued evolution of the paradigm. Reaching a more broad audience is incredibly important at this stage.

References

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